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STUDY OF BIOCHEMICAL, CLINICAL, AND HEMATOLOGICAL PROFILE OF COVID-19 PATIENTS IN A TERTIARY CARE HOSPITAL

Rizwan Hanif Khan, Seema Hanif Khan*

Aberdeen Royal Infirmary, NHS Grampian-UK, *Medway NHS Foundation Trust-UK

Background: The clinical outcomes of patients vary based on age, gender, previous dengue infection, co-infections, biochemical/hematological parameters and comorbidities such as Hypertension, Diabetes and Pregnancy etc. **Objectives:** To evaluate the clinical outcomes of patients having COVID-19 along with their physical and biochemical parameters (Clinical Profile) **Methods:** A cross sectional study was carried on a total of 380 patients admitted in the various medical wards of Khyber Teaching Hospital/MTI, Peshawar from June 2020 to December 2020. IBM SPSS 26 and MS Excel were used for statistical analysis. **Results:** Fever, Headache, Cough, Sinusitis and Myalgia were the most common presenting complain whereas ARDS and Multiple organ failure were the major complications. DM, HTN and CAD were reported to be the major comorbidities in these patients. Biochemical markers such as Serum Ferritin, C-Reactive Protein and D-Dimers showed a wide range of deviation from the mean. Ferritin was 500.70 ± 110.19 (ng/ml), D-Dimers were 450 ± 103 (ng/ml) and C-Reactive Protein of 15.05 ± 4.25 (mg/dl). **Conclusion:** COVID-19 is a global health issue and is becoming increasingly difficult to control and manage due to the high infectivity and airborne nature of the virus causing it. The menace of COVID-19 can only be dealt with proper public health awareness, mass campaign, media involvement, education of the masses and a sound clinical approach.

Keywords: COVID-19; SARS-CoV-2; Ferritin; D-Dimers

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INTRODUCTION

Corona Virus Disease 2019 or more simply known as the COVID-19 emerged from the City of Wuhan in the Hubei Province of China in the last quarter of 2019 as cases presenting with pneumonia but unknown aetiology. The virus responsible for the clinical condition is Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome Corona Virus 2 or the SARS-CoV-2 [1].

The virus has since then become a global issue of imminent concern. The primary thought behind conducting this study was to give a broad view of this less known but rapidly evolving medical condition. Coronavirus, as the name indicates, has a crown-like appearance. SARS-CoV-2 is an RNA virus and shares a sequence identity of 79% to SARS-CoV, that caused the 2003 outbreak [2].

COVID-19 presents with Fever, Headache, Cough, Sinusitis, Myalgia and a variety of other signs and symptoms. In severe cases, COVID-19 results in life-threatening Acute Respiratory Distress Syndrome (ARDS), extremely low blood pressure and Oxygen Saturation Levels, leading to increased risk of Mortality. In such cases fluid replacement therapies or aggressive Intensive Care management may be required. This whole country is under the attack of this fatal yet manageable medical condition. Clinical diagnosis of COVID-19 and identification of patients that are likely to develop severe disease remains challenging. The goal of the study was to identify the factors which predict the severity of the disease and the outcome of patients with COVID-19 infection. To identify the patients at risk of developing the complications such as ARDS

MATERIALS & METHODS

A study was performed in the Department of Medicine at Khyber Teaching Hospital in Peshawar from January 2020 to December 2020 to carry out the assessment of the clinical profile of patients presenting with COVID-19 during the recent outbreak in the parts of Peshawar, Pakistan. Inclusion criteria included patients positive for COVID-19 by RT-PCR. Three Hundred and Eighty (380) patients admitted in the various medical wards were included in the study. Blood for was taken and analyzed at the Hospital Laboratory via Cobas 6000 E 501 analyzer. The following parameters were carefully included in the study: Serum Ferritin, C-Reactive Protein, D-Dimers,

Hemoglobin, White Blood Cells and Platelet count. Written informed, voluntary consent was obtained. The Institutional Review and Ethics Board approved the study. All Confounding variables will be controlled by exclusion criteria. Bias will be controlled by following strict inclusion criteria for patient selection, All the data was collected on a research proforma for this study's protocol. All information was recorded using proforma and analyzed on IBM SPSS Statistics for Windows, Version 26.0. (Armonk, NY: IBM Corp.).

RESULTS

Fever, Headache, Cough, Sinusitis and Myalgia were the most common presenting complain whereas ARDS and Multiple organ failure were the major complications. DM, HTN and CAD were reported to be the major comorbidities in these patients. Biochemical markers such as Serum Ferritin, C-Reactive Protein and D-Dimers showed a wide range of deviation from the mean. Ferritin was 500.70 ± 110.19 (ng/ml), D-Dimers were 450 ± 103 (ng/ml) and C-Reactive Protein of 15.05 ± 4.25 (mg/dl).

Fever	380
Headache	210
Myalgia	300
Vomiting	70
Diarrhea	90
Cough	375
SOB	120
Sinusitis	170

Fig. 1 shows frequency table of different Symptoms/Signs

Renal Failure	20
Multi Organ Failure	30

Acute Respiratory Distress Syndrome (ARDS)	50
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Fig. 2 shows table with the frequency of developed complications

Parameter	Mean +/- SD
Hemoglobin (gm/dl)	12.0 ±1.31
WBC (/cmm)	13000 ±2300
PLT (/cmm)	100000 ± 40000
Ferritin (ng/ml)	500.70±110.19
D-Dimers (ng/ml)	450±103
C-Reactive Protein (mg/dl)	15.05±4.25

Fig. 3 Table showing biochemical parameters of the COVID-19 patients. (n=380)

Fig. 4 Bar Chart showing the frequency of different symptoms in COVID-19 patients

DISCUSSION

This study was conducted from the month of June to December as the COVID-19 infection was most prominent and in urban areas as the reported cases in many areas of the country during these months was at a rise and it was observed that the cases tend to fall when the temperatures are warmer. Out of 380 hospitalized patients included in this study the most common symptom at the time of presentation was fever. It had a frequency of 100% for the admitted patients. The frequency of other symptoms at the time of presentation was in the order of headache 55%, myalgia 79%, vomiting 18%, diarrhea 24%, cough 98%, shortness of breath (SOB) 31% and sinusitis 45%. The complications that were reported include; Renal failure in twenty patients, ARDS in fifty patients and multiple organ failure was reported in thirty patients.

In the biochemical parameters of the patient there was a significantly high count of white blood cells above the normal ranges. The Levels of Serum Ferritin and D-Dimers have been to be associated with mortality and morbidity. These need to be checked early on and taken as a marker of disease progression and recovery. As the days progress and serum Ferritin/D-Dimers levels fall within normal ranges, the symptoms improved and were associated with better clinical outcomes and are indicative of recovery.

In this study sudden fall of oxygen saturation was the most critical clinical implication. This was in conjunction with the previous published data of the patients [3]. Prevention is critical as there is no specific and approved treatment for COVID-19 at this time. Although many trials are underway but none has so far been very successful with a breakthrough in this regard.

Community involvement including avoidance of large gatherings, is of utmost importance as social distancing is an effective tool to not only decrease the risk of spread but to also reduce the ever-growing disease burden on the healthcare facilities. Preventive measure includes maintenance of good sunlight and adequate airway ventilation to kill the virus on the surfaces. Patients should be advised to wear surgical mask while care givers including healthcare workers and those who tend for the patients

should wear surgical mask and personal protective equipment and practise hand hygiene frequently [4].

Isolation of the positive cases is the first and foremost step in this regard. Treatment generally revolves around giving symptomatic and supportive care to control fever, hydration and nutrition. Different drugs including the use of Antivirals with or without a combination of antibiotics has been warranted but to no major success so far [5].

The use of steroidal therapy has not shown benefits rather a possibility of harm to the patients has been observed and is therefore not recommended to use corticosteroids for COVID-19 [6]. Remdesivir, an antiviral medication has shown some promise and the clinical trial is undergoing but it would be too early to use it as a recommended treatment option [7-9].

With limited data on the subject, no specific treatment or licensed vaccines to treat COVID-19 Infection, there is a need to look for alternative options including the use of Passive immunization via monoclonal antibody therapy especially in pandemic situations like this [10]. There is progress but so far, the antibodies haven't been marketed.

CONCLUSION

COVID-19 is a global health issue and is becoming increasingly difficult to control and manage due to the high infectivity and airborne nature of the virus causing it. The menace of COVID-19 can only be dealt with proper public health awareness, mass campaign, media involvement, education of the masses and a sound clinical approach. Randomized clinical control

trials and meta analysis's will be required to establish a better treatment guideline and better insight into the management of the disease.

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